

JURIDICAL DISCOURSE AND SPEECH ETHICS IN THE TRIAL

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ABSTRACT

First factor that shows human consciousness, complementary part of applied linguistics, the individual's behavior, lawyer's discourse, forensic linguistics, the legal and judicial consultation.

It is no secret that the culture of dealing is of great importance to representatives of law enforcement agencies, as well as to representatives of any field. It is language that is the first factor that shows human consciousness. As V. Kolesov noted, "Every word smells of profession". It is, in fact an integral part of the culture of speech, a phenomenon that strives for culture.

At this point, it is necessary to talk about the necessary skills in practice for specialists in the field, first of all, it is necessary to fully master the terms of the field and have the ability to use them appropriately. We don't want to pass. The ability to correctly deliver the terms reflected in written speech to ordinary citizens, and the ability to comprehensively explain is considered the highest communicative competence of a lawyer. In particular, speech that is grammatically complete and uses correct lexical units can make a significant contribution to the level of work of representatives of the field.

Forensic linguistics which is a complementary part of applied linguistics, covers a vast number of topics, such as the language of trials, lawyers, judges and the language of the law itself. It defines forensic linguistics as "the use of linguistic techniques to juridical discourse in which language data forms part of evidence, such as in the use of grammatical or lexical criteria to authenticate police or trial statements". It is like a game of words. Thus, a good lawyer, like judge or jury member, is the one who can make use of the right legal words at the right time. Recently, legal language is considered a specific variety of language which can be used as a highly differentiated variety for specific purposes. Moreover, the language of law is regarded as a sub-branch of legal language. Language is created to serve human affairs, but at the same time it can be used to solve issues of law. Law is highly dependent on words whereas morality and customs are included within the human behavior. Thus, one can

notice that words make law. Lawyers use language to explicate what the law means and to have debates before the court and jury. Simply put, law and its language have a great effect on the daily life of everyone in the society. In the previous literature about lawyer's discourse. Lawyer's discourse in the Uzbek courtrooms has not been investigated, and no contrastive study of the English and Uzbek discourse has been constructed. Hence, there is a need for research in this area.

The legal field, to which law belongs, constitutes an independent culture with powerful vocational norms that give sense and reinforcement to the individual's behavior. So, even a lawyer and client, who belong to the same culture will go through the client-lawyer misunderstanding because of the cultural dissimilarities which result from legal culture. Indeed, lawyers need to improve their knowledge, awareness and skills in order to encounter the cross cultural difficulties and communicate with clients accurately. Thus, lawyer's rhetorical ingenuity continues to spark the imagination of people and the rhetorical skills of lawyers are being one of the most well-known cultural models of persuasive speech. According to Al-Aubaidy article, there are certain characteristics that every lawyer should have: (Al-Aubaidy 2012, pp. 46-47)

1). Truthfulness and Honesty. Honesty is a solid foundation for lawyering and is one of the distinct characteristics of humanism. A successful lawyer has to make good relations with his clients and colleagues.

2). Patience and Collaboration. Patience is one of the greatest traits that any lawyer should have since it has a tremendous effect on the individual's confidence and personality. Thus, a lawyer should be

patient to reach his goals and his client's rights. Moreover, collaboration is also a key factor for each lawyer since one cannot live alone.

3). Bravery in Saying the Truth. Self-confidence is one of the important features for the lawyer's personality, and the client must manifest this feature at the first sight to give him confidence of his lawyer. So, the lawyer should tell his client all the truth about his case, and if the client's opinion is vicious, then the lawyer leads him to the right way.

The lawyer is a person who is restricted by law according to the rules of the bar association and usually advises people and gives them the legal and judicial consultation. At the same time, the lawyer defends people in the court either orally or through written texts. Lawyering exists all over the world and is an urgent need to save human rights. One can notice that all the legal systems in the whole world almost have the same conditions that people should have in order to be lawyers and one of those conditions is to have high level of education and knowledge about law. Thus, lawyering is a basic element in the judiciary system. One of the main responsibilities of lawyers is to help a client to protect and assert the rights clarified by law in that the lawyer normally perform as an advocate to his client. Alternately, the principal duty of a lawyer provides his client with legal information leading him to take care of his affairs. Moreover, the lawyer is supposed to interact effectively with his client in order to help the later select the right decision. Thus, it is significant to say that the ultimate job of a lawyer is informing, advising, and assisting the client. This explains the importance of communication skills for lawyers.

The science of speech culture studies the norms of literary language in all areas of language. It provides recommendations for strengthening the literary norms, it does not force certain events as norms (Samigova, Rixxivoyev, 2021.) Perhaps the activity of the national literary language of each nation monitors its development, discovers objective law and teaches on the basis of them.

Discourse analysis refers to the analysis of the patterns that people's utterances follow when taking part in the domains of life. Discourse analysis has come to be employed with a vast range of meanings that deal with a vast range of activities. It characterizes activities at the intersection of various disciplines, such as sociolinguistics, psycholinguistics, philosophical linguistics and computational linguistics. Communication competence, as we said, is the main work tool of a lawyer, and it is a skill that must be mastered in advance before starting professional activity, not through trial and error. Its lack in practice can cause tragic consequences for the public employee, as well as for all legal and physical persons who come into contact with him.

We think of discourse analysis as a study of language, but it is not just the study of language. It is a way of looking at language that emphasizes how people use it in real life to do things, such as jokes, argument and persuasion, and to show that they are particular sorts of people or belong to certain groups. Discourse analysts are concerned with the learning ways by which sentences and utterances go together to make texts and interactions and how these texts and interactions fit into our social world.

Therefore, the fact that each field has its own language, lexicon, and discourse, which is reflected in a number of scientific studies, shows the importance of the issue. The legal field is one of these fields, and teaching the basics of speech culture to future lawyers in relevant educational institutions is considered an important factor. In the legal system, language is the substrate of the field - a means of persuasion, formalization, influence on the minds of citizens. Language is considered the main tool of representatives of the field, and the list in the previous sentence can be continued by describing many other tools. Law is a procedure that serves to maintain and establish order, provides equal freedom and uniform justice to subjects of different classifications entering into social relations. The important point is that this order is reflected only in word form and its application has its own requirements and principles.

At this point, it is necessary to talk about the necessary skills in practice for specialists in the field, first of all, it is necessary to fully master the terms of the field and have the ability to use them appropriately. We do not want to pass. The ability to correctly deliver the terms reflected in written speech to ordinary citizens, and the ability to comprehensively explain is considered the highest communicative competence of a lawyer. In particular, speech that is grammatically complete and uses correct lexical units can make a significant contribution to the level of work of representatives of the field. Law enforcement officers should be able to prevent problematic situations through speech tools, find solutions to existing situations through them, be able to convey their message easily during communication

and use everyday terms that are understandable to ordinary citizens, communicate with citizens in a familiar lexicon. It is important to be able to do it, to eliminate the abrupt, cold tone and excessive politeness. This, in turn, should be taken into account in the educational programs of educational institutions that

prepare representatives of this field. Our society needs a lawman with high interpersonal skills and communication skills, and the development of language education in educational institutions, paying more attention to ethic, is a direct solution to the problem.

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